

MB, Kaniadakis and Tsallis Distributions Directly from Sum over i ei probability(i) = Etotal?

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We suggest that the Kaniadakis $\ln_k(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and the Tsallis $\ln_q(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ (as well as the Maxwell-Boltzmann) follow as possible solutions of the statement: Sum over i probability(i) $F(p(e_i)) = \text{Sum over i } (-e_i/T) \text{ probability(i)}$. For the Kaniadakis case, $\text{probability}(i) = p(e_i)$, while for the Tsallis, $\text{probability}(i) = p(e_i)^q$. $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, one has a similar situation.

We argue that various statistical F functions and hence p(ei) distributions may be obtained simply by considering: Sum over i ei probability(i) = Sum over i ei {probability(i) + delta probability(i)} = Energy total without any notion of maximization of entropy or other considerations. (Note: The above expression is set equal to: Sum over i (probability(i) + delta(probability(i))) { F(p) + dF/dp dp} to find solutions.

The Notion of Average Energy

Consider a probability distribution p(ei) such that Sum over i ei p(ei) = E(average) ((1))

and Sum over i p(ei) = 1. ((2))

Then, one may consider p(ei) + delta(p(ei)), but:

Sum over i delta(p(ei)) = 0 and Sum over i ei delta(p(ei)) = 0 ((3))

We argue that ((3)) suffices for finding various distributions, such as the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis and Kaniadakis ones. For all cases, we propose that there exists a function:

$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((4)) (F is essentially the inverse of p(ei) as $p(e_i) = p(e_i/T)$).

General Approach

Sum over i probability(i) F(p(ei)) = Sum over i (-ei/T) probability(i) ((5))

If one considers: p(ei) → p(ei)+delta(p(ei)) and probability(i) → probability(i) + delta(probability(i))

then to first order:

Sum over i delta(probability(ei)) F(p) + dF/dp p delta(p) = Sum over i (-ei/T)

delta(probability(i)) ((6))

(In the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Kaniadakis cases, probability(i) = p(ei), but in the Tsallis case it does not.)

The first term on the LHS and the RHS are both 0, so:

$$\sum_i dF/dp \cdot p \cdot \delta(p) = 0 \quad ((7a))$$

One may then consider a variety of solutions which satisfy ((7)) meaning that one seeks:

$$dF/dp = \text{constant} / p \quad \text{or} \quad dF/dp = \text{constant} * e^{i/p} \quad ((7b))$$

Maxwell-Boltzmann Case

The simplest solution is to have: $dF/dp = 1/p$ or $F(p) = \ln(p)$ ((8a))

Then ((7)) is: $\sum_i \delta(p(e_i)) = 0$.

Kaniadakis Case

We next consider the Kaniadakis case because probability(i) = p(ei).

If one considers the math function: $F(p) = 1/k (p^k - p^{-k})$, ((8b)) then:

$$dF/dp = p^{-1} \{p^k + p^{-k}\} \quad ((9))$$

The inverse of F may be shown to be: $p = \{ \sqrt{1+kx} - kx \}^{1/k}$ ((10a)) where $x=e_i/T$

Using this, one may show that ((9)) is indeed: $dF/dp = 1/p (-e_i/T)^k$ which when multiplied by p is a constant and so ((7)) holds. One may note that for $k \rightarrow 1$ one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann result as is well-known.

One might ask: How does one deduce ((8b))? We suggest that it is linked to a quadratic equation. In particular:

$$B + 1/B = \{\text{constant or constant} * e_i\} \quad (\text{we choose } e_i \text{ as a variable}) \quad \rightarrow$$

$$B^2 + 1 - B * \text{constant} * e_i = 0 \quad ((10b))$$

$B + 1/B$ follows from taking d/dp of $p^k - p^{-k}$. One may then assume that p is a function in e_i/T to the power $1/k$ to eliminate k in p^k or p^{-k} .

We thus note that the Kaniadakis uses: $dF/dp = \text{constant} \cdot e_i/p$. There should also be a solution for $dF/dp = \text{constant}/p$ and we suggest that this is the Tsallis solution, Thus, the two conditions of ((7b)) lead to the Kaniadakis and Tsallis cases respectively.

Tsallis Case

The Tsallis case is a little different because:

$$\text{probability}(i) = p(e_i) \text{ power } q \quad \text{where } p(e_i) \text{ is normalized. } ((11))$$

$$\text{Nevertheless, } F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Sum over } i \quad e_i p(e_i) \text{ power } q = E \text{ total } ((12))$$

One may note that $p(e_i) \text{ power } q$ is not normalized, but ((12)) still holds. If one considers:

$P \rightarrow p + \delta(p)$ then:

$$\text{Sum over } i \quad q \delta(p(e_i)) p(e_i) \text{ power } (q-1) e_i = 0 \quad ((13))$$

The same change must be considered in: $\text{Sum over } i \quad p(e_i) \text{ power } q F(p)$ i.e. first order terms:

$$\text{Sum over } i \quad \delta(p(e_i)) F(p) + p(e_i) \text{ power } q dF/dp dp = 0 = ((13)) \quad ((14))$$

The first term on the LHS is 0 from ((13)), thus:

$$\text{Sum over } p \quad p(e_i) \text{ power } q dF/dp \delta p = 0 \quad ((15))$$

$$\text{A solution would then be: } dF/dp = \text{constant} \cdot p(e_i) \text{ power } (-q) \quad ((16))$$

If one considers the function: $\text{Sum over } i \quad 1/(1-q) \{1-p(e_i) \text{ power } (1-q)\} = F(p)$ ((17)) then:

$$dF/dp = - p(e_i) \text{ power } (-q) \quad \text{which satisfies } ((16)).$$

One may also note that for $q \rightarrow 1$, $F(p) = \ln(p)$ as is well known. The functional form ((17)) is straightforward to deduce.

The Tsallis case is linked with the ((7b)) condition: $dF/dp = \text{constant}/p$.

Conclusion

We suggest a straightforward scheme for obtaining the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Kaniadakis and Tsallis distributions without requiring any notion of maximization of entropy or information. We simply consider: $\text{Sum over } i \quad \text{probability}(e_i) e_i = \text{Sum over } i \quad \{\text{probability}(e_i) + \delta(\text{probability}(e_i))\} e_i = E \text{ total}$. We then postulate a function $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, i.e. F is essentially

the inverse of p . We consider probability \rightarrow probability + $\delta(\text{probability})$ in sum over i
probability (i) $F(p(e_i))$ and match it with Sum over i probability (i) $(-e_i/T)$. For the
Maxwell-Boltzmann and Kaniadakis cases, probability $(i) = p(e_i)$, while for the Tsallis,
probability $(i) = p(e_i)$ power q . We show that the three math solutions appear in a straightforward
manner from this simple approach.